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Ascetics, Missionaries, Lovers: Interconfessional Confrontation and Interaction in Seventeenth Century Ottoman Armenian Eyewitness Narratives

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Abstract

Seventeenth-century Armenian historiographic accounts, chronicles and diaries demonstrate an increasing prevalence of the first-person narrative over the ‘neutral’ third person and authorial narratives. This provides significant insights into the daily interpersonal, intra-communal and inter-communal relations between different religious and confessional groups within the Ottoman empire. Relying on unedited and understudied written sources, I identified several hermeneutical tools that may be useful to assess the complex dynamics of identity construction that marked the relations of Armenian individuals and groups with other co-existing confessional and religious local communities within and on the northern and eastern fringes of the Ottoman Empire in the first half of the seventeenth century.

Keywords

Ottoman Armenians – religious and confessional diversity – sacred biographies – devotional space – intergroup marriages – intersubjective narrative – Armenian historiography of the Ottoman Empire – polemics

1 Ottoman Armenian Narrative Identities in the Seventeenth Century

The early seventeenth century was characterized by significant societal and cultural transformations within the Ottoman empire. Increasing migrations of eastern Anatolian Armenians to western Anatolia and the northern Black Sea region led to dramatic population growth in urban areas and generated intra-communal and inter-communal tensions, particularly in Constantinople, Bursa and in other port cities of the Empire.¹ Culturally, the ongoing and sustained movement of people from the countryside to the city, both within and across the borders of the Empire, prompted a significant shift in the cultural and literary landscape of this period. Vernacular language, which had already intruded into Armenian poetry, lyrics, medicine, and homiletics since the twelfth and thirteenth centuries, started to penetrate other classical literary genres such as, for instance, historiographic texts. An overarching tendency to popularize historical accounts indicates that the objectives, scope and target audience(s) of seventeenth-century authors were markedly different from those of medieval historians and chroniclers.² From a narratological perspective, historical events and facts are no longer recorded by a distant narrator who relies primarily on indirect sources and archival material but by eyewitness narrators who recount historical events and daily occurrences through the lens of their own personal experience. This article aims to assess how communal relationships and interactions between individuals of different coexisting Christian communities across the Ottoman space in the seventeenth century are set up and conceived of in varied Armenian literary sources from that period by scrutinising eyewitness and personal narratives. It has been argued by scholars that early modern Armenian chronicles and archival material can contribute to the retelling of the history of political interactions, clashes and conflicts between different political actors and superpowers across early modern Eurasia, by

1 H. Shapiro, *The Rise of the Western Armenian Diaspora in the Early Modern Ottoman Empire. From Refugee Crisis to Renaissance*. Edinburgh University Press: Edinburgh, 2022. In the present contribution, I use the Hübschmann-Meillet transliteration system and just in some cases, I prefer to transliterate according either to the commonly accepted transliteration (e.g., Etchmiadzin instead of Ējmiacin) or to the Western Armenian pronunciation (e.g., Baron instead of Paron), especially for personal names.

2 For a recent study on the extensive application of the vernacular language, the so-called Middle or Cilician Armenian, to learned literary context and its links with state elites: M. Pifer, "The King's Mellifluous Tongue. Study, Social Bonding and the Making of Middle Armenian as a Language of the Elite in Medieval Cilicia", *Armeniaca* 3 (2024), pp. 93–152, DOI 10.30687/arm/2974-6051/2024/01/004.

associating large-scale narratives with a local and micro-regional perspective through eyewitness and self-narratives.³ Such sources have been proved to be useful in shedding light onto the agitated religious landscape of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries Ottoman Empire, by witnessing how varied denominational communities of the lands of Rûm reacted to the increasing proselytization of the Catholic missionaries.⁴ Anna Ohanjanyan pointed at the doctrinal means used by K'ēōmiwrċean to reinforce the process of community building within the Armenian Apostolic Church and Constantinopolitan community and to strengthen a common sense of belonging that relied on peculiar practices and beliefs.⁵ More recently, Henry Shapiro argued for a strong interdependence between the massive migration of Armenians from Greater Armenia westwards at the beginning of the seventeenth century and the rise of a western Armenian Diaspora in the Ottoman Empire, which in turn catalysed the florescence of the cultural and intellectual life of the Armenian communities of Istanbul and of other major urban hubs of the Empire. Shapiro also contends that the transformation of Constantinyye/Istanbul into the most important Armenian demographic and cultural centre in the world from the nineteenth to the first decade of the twentieth centuries was sparked by two prominent 'refugee' authors, Daranałc'i and K'ēōmiwrċean. Both scholars contributed to initiate a cultural cosmopolitanism, which would have marked

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- 3 H.S. Anasyan, "Ditolut'yunner Step'anos Salmastec'u kensagrut'yan verabereal" [Remarks on the Biography of Step'anos Salmastac'i], *Etchmiadzin* 8–9 (1956), pp. 93–99, *Etchmiadzin* 11–12 (1956), pp. 69–76; N. Poghosyan, "An Armenian Chronicle of Crimea", in: *The Ottoman World: A Cultural History Reader, 1450–1700*, edited by H.T. Karateke, University of California Press: California, 2021, pp. 181–187; Shapiro, *The Rise*.
- 4 C. Santus, *Trasgressioni necessarie. Communicatio in sacris, coesistenza e conflitti tra le comunità cristiane orientali (Levante e Impero Ottomano, XVII–XVIII secolo)*. École française de Rome: Rome, 2019; P. Lucca, "Cleansing the Christian Vineyard. Dominican Missions to the Armenian Catholic Diocese of Naxijewan in the 1610s–1630s", in: *Il viaggio in Armenia. Dall'antichità ai nostri giorni*, a cura di A. Ferrari, S. Haroutyunian and P. Lucca, Venezia, 2021, pp. 39–62; P. Lucca, "From Doctrinal Persuasion to Economic Threats: Paolo Piromalli's Missionary Work Among the Armenians and His Conversion Strategies", in: *Entangled Confessionalizations? Dialogic perspectives on the Politics of Piety and Community Building in the Ottoman Empire, 15th–18th Centuries*, edited by T. Krstić & D. Terzioğlu, Gorgias Press: Piscataway, NJ, 2022, pp. 451–487. Extensive bibliographical references of previous scholarship on this topic, in: Shapiro, *The Rise*, pp. 301–314.
- 5 A. Ohanjanyan, "Credal controversies among Armenians in the Seventeenth Century Ottoman Empire. Eremia Ć'elēpi K'ēōmiwrċean's Polemical Writing against Suk'ias Prusac'i", *Journal of the Society for Armenian Studies* 27 (2020), pp. 7–69; Ohanjanyan, "Intra-Armenian Polemics and Confession-Building in Ottoman Constantinople: The Case of Geōrg Mxlayim Ōlli (1681/85–1758)", in T. Krstić & D. Terzioğlu (eds.), *Entangled*, pp. 489–519.

the intellectual ambiance and life of Constantiniiyye's Armenians between the seventeenth and the mid-nineteenth centuries.⁶

While acknowledging the growing endeavours in placing Armenian literary sources into a global early modern framework by means of methodological and analytical toolboxes, such as 'confessionalization', 'confession-building' and 'confessional ambiguity', which have been proven to be useful tools in tracing the emergence of confessional dynamics in Europe and Eurasia, I shall argue that varied seventeenth century literary texts display compelling vignettes suggesting different tendencies among Armenian individuals and groups in interacting as faith community with other co-existing Christian denominations within a prevailing Muslim environment and in relationship with Muslim authorities.⁷ The variety of strategies adopted by ecclesiastical personalities and lay people in dealing with confrontation, discord and contention and in negotiating agreements despite differences, shows that intra-, inter- and cross-communal entanglements among the various denominational groups of the Ottoman Empire cannot be described as homogenous, but must be circumstantially discussed. For this purpose, I will analyse four case studies deriving from two different literary genres, namely eyewitness narratives and theological pamphlets. Despite their textual divergence, these two kinds of written sources are characterised by intertextual analogies in their commensurable and interdependent accounts of encounters, confrontations and coexistence between Christian Armenians and other religious or confessional groups living and acting within the multi-confessional context of pre-modern Islamicate empires. Thereafter, I shall focus on the literary production of three seventeenth centuries authors, namely Grigor Daranał'ı (1576–1643), Eremia Celebi K'ēōmiwrčean (1637–1695), and Paolo Piromalli (1591–1667). In particular, this study will take into account the *Diary* (*Ōragrut'ıwn*) and the *Book of Histories* (*Girk' Patmut'eanc'*; hereafter *Polihistoriae*) by Eremia K'ēōmiwrčean, the *Chronicle* (*Žamanakagrut'ıwn*) by Grigor Daranał'ı, and the *Apology of the Two Natures of Christ Against Armenian Vardapet Simon* (*Tearn Pōtosi frang vardapetın yałags erkus bnut'eanc' K'ristosi Patasxanin ar tēr Simovn hayoc'*

6 Shapiro, *The Rise*, pp. 288–291.

7 The concept of 'confessionalization' and of cognate notions emerged in the early 1980s in the context of the German scholarship on the Holy Roman Empire and was then developed within the framework of social history. It was meant to indicate specific strategies adopted by varied churches in Europe (Catholic, Lutheran and Calvinist) to build 'confessional communities' by means of social disciplining that could be used for political purposes. For a critical overview of the use of the abovementioned notions for the study of confessional groups in the Ottoman Empire: Krstić, "Can we Speak of Confessionalization beyond the Reformation?", in T. Krstić & D. Terzioğlu (eds.), *Entangled*, pp. 25–115.

vardapetn; hereafter *Apology*) by Paolo Piromalli. These texts offer, indeed, the four case-studies that inform my analysis in assessing the complex dynamics of identity construction that, along the seventeenth century, Armenian individuals and groups displayed when confronted with other confessional and religious co-existing local communities. Daranał'ci and K'ēōmiwrčean were not only prolific authors and cultural brokers but were also engaged in their contemporary diplomatic, civil and trade life, providing thereby valuable and first-hand information on inter- and cross-communal interconnections between varied religious communities of the Ottoman Empire. Confessionally, both Daranał'ci and K'ēōmiwrčean exemplified the point of view of the autocephalous and independent non-Chalcedonian Armenian Church, whereas Piromalli was a Dominican missionary sent by the *Sacra Congregatio de Propaganda Fide* to Persia and Greater Armenia for the purpose of bringing local Armenians into union with Rome. In his unionist endeavour, Piromalli authored the not yet edited *Apology* preserved in manuscripts Vatican Borg. Arm. 10 and 11 and as autograph in manuscript Vatican Borg. Arm. 40 of the Vatican Library's collection. This study will concentrate on Piromalli's *Apology*, for this text well illustrate Piromalli's rhetoric methods to induce the adversary to recognize his "dogmatic deviation" from the authorities on which the Armenian Church itself relied. While Piromalli's preaching activity showcases the ambiguous and turbulent encounter between a post-Tridentine Italian missionary and the Armenian Apostolic clergy, K'ēōmiwrčean and Daranał'ci represent the flip side of the same coin.⁸ Grigor Daranał'ci's *Chronicle* is a kind of biographical narration of events that the author himself experienced or was told by reliable eyewitnesses. The edition of Grigor's *Chronicle* was made on the only extant and complete autograph manuscript of the work, which is held at the Library of the Patriarchate of Jerusalem (J1069).⁹ From the colophon of this manuscript, we are told that the author composed his *Chronicle* between 1634 and 1640. Grigor's opus is made up of two parts covering the events that occurred between the end of the sixteenth century and the conquest of Baghdad by Sultan Murad between in 1638. While the first part focuses on episodes concerning the political life of the Empire, the second part encompasses a vast array of information on Armenian ecclesiastical policy with a particular focus on the Catholicosate of Sis and its relationship with the Catholicosate of Etchmiadzin in the aftermath of the "schism" between the two patriarchal

8 On Piromalli's catechetical activity: Lucca, "From Doctrinal Persuasion", pp. 451–487.

9 *Žamanakagrut'ivn Grigor Vardapeti Kamaxec'woy kam Daranałwoy* [Chronicle of Vardapet Grigor of Kamax or of Daranali], edited by M. Nšanian, S. Yakobean' Tparan: Erusałēm, 1915 (hereafter, *Chronicle*).

sees (1441), as well as on the imperial Ottoman foreign policy at the time of the Ottoman-Safavid war (1623–1639). Furthermore, Grigor offers remarkable glimpses on the social life of varied Armenian communities of western and eastern Anatolia and the Armenian highlands, as well. He outlines lively descriptions and dialogues between different individuals, by interlacing the standard third-person narrative with the less conventional first-person perspective and his own personal anecdotes.

The *Diary*, penned by K'ēomiwrčean between 1648 to 1662, is an invaluable and yet unexplored eyewitness source to reconstructing the daily life of several Ottoman Armenians who were intellectually and diplomatically engaged not only in their own community but also in the flow of events of their own contemporary political scene. By capturing the author's lived experience of events and facts and offering circumstantial and personal views from the inside, K'ēomiwrčean's *Diary* greatly contributes to shed light on diplomatic negotiations but also tensions that, in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, opposed different centres of the Armenian faith, namely the Catholicosate of Sis, the Catholicosate of Etchmiadzin, the Armenian Patriarchate in Jerusalem and the Armenian Patriarchate in Constantinople. In his *Diary*, and in other literary works as well, K'ēomiwrčean magnifies the narrative shift that informs seventeenth century historiographical texts, as I shall demonstrate in this article. Gradually, stories from the daily lives of ordinary people and the narrators themselves became intertwined with accounts of large-scale political and economic events, which had previously characterized Armenian standard historiography. This narrative shift enables us to reconstruct not only the social landscape of local religious (and/or confessional) communities but also to delve into the cognitive world of the narrator and his own subjectivity. Stories of daily life allow us to outline the expectations of K'ēomiwrčean's contemporary readers as, for instance, when Eremia records how people interacted with different objects of devotion or how Armenian individuals and groups negotiated their legitimacy to use shared cult spaces against other Christian denominations or Muslim authorities. The narrator's personal involvement in the events of his own time – mirrored by the change from third person to first-person narrative – also resulted in a significant intrusion of words and sayings from spoken language, showcasing an amalgamation of Armenian dialects, Turkish and Persian. Eremia's *Polihistoriae*, completed in 1693, has not yet been edited and to the best of our knowledge is only available in manuscript number 509 of the Library of the Mekhitarist Fathers in San Lazzaro Venice.¹⁰

10 I would like to thank Fr. Vahan Ohanian of the Mekhitarist Congregation of Venice for providing me with a copy of the manuscript.

The *Polihistoriae* has remained largely unknown to historians for several reasons, including difficult access to the manuscript and philological and linguistic barriers. The original Armenian handwritten text is challenging, even for scholars of Armenian or Ottoman studies, as it requires excellent expertise in both fields of research, and in the colloquial language of that period. Furthermore, the codex is incomplete and was written hastily. Despite these technical hurdles, the text deserves great attention on several grounds. First, it provides first-hand information on the inner dynamics of the Ottoman foreign policy in the second half of the seventeenth-century, by focusing on the wars and military campaigns that the Ottoman army fought against the Habsburgs, the Serenissima, and the Polish Lithuanian forces under the sultanate of Mehmet IV (1648–1687). Second, it accounts events related to the *dōšurmē/devishirmé* policy (սոշնրսւի in Armeno-Turkish and *mankažotov* in Armenian, both terms are alternatively used by Eremia) in the eastern provinces of the Empire and to the consequences of that policy on the daily life of farmers and peasants of the Anatolian countryside. Third, the *Polihistoriae* contains an extensive section dedicated to Christians who were martyred recently, which is a continuation of the late medieval Armenian synaxaria. The section of the Venetian manuscript dedicated to the new martyrs stands out. According to Eremia himself, he compiled the new synaxarion at the request of many pious compatriots who asked him to record the lives of recent and contemporary martyrs and to write down the lives of these common men and women in a refined literary style. In the initial colophon, Eremia informs us that he composed the collection in his old age, when he was afflicted by physical pains, suggesting that this work was intended as his final legacy. Many of the stories focus on the forced conversion of Christian children, whether Armenian or Greek, to Islam, their subsequent reconversion to Christianity, and their martyrdom at the hands of local Muslims. However, we also read of a pious Muslim man who converted to Christianity after a pilgrimage to Medina and Jerusalem, as well as of an elderly Greek man who was used to bring sweet fruits to the imperial palace and was falsely despised and persecuted by some envious Turks on account of his faith. There is also the story of a Christian boy who was forcibly converted to Islam and then after spending time in France, reconverted to Christianity. This variety of conversions, reconversions, and martyrdoms was intended to instruct all the Christians of the Empire and to immortalise the life of ordinary people living in the Empire's peripheral towns and villages.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that, at the very beginning of the manuscript, there is an apparently incomplete section, in which Eremia reports many events related to the destruction of churches and to the negotiations

contracted by several religious and political actors to obtain control of specific churches. The author also records the involvement of local Ottoman authorities as well as of local Muslim people in championing either the Greek or the Armenian faction in the control over church buildings.¹¹ Events reported in this section are sometimes recorded by Eremia in his *Diary*. However, the treatment of the matter and the wealth of information that Eremia generously provides, are completely different from those that we have in the *Diary*, implying thereby that the author had other purposes when compiling the *Polihistoriae*. Eremia reveals his main aim in the introductory chapter to the second part of his work, by spelling out the connection between the tragic calamities that uninterruptedly afflicted the Armenians along their history and the curse uttered by Patriarch Nersēs the Great (d. 373) that the political and religious powers of the Armenians would have been destroyed and great sufferings would have plagued the Armenians “until the appearance of the impurity of the desert”.¹² The apocalyptic vision of Nersēs the Great, which

11 As for accounts concerning the destruction or reconstruction of communal churches, it is worth mentioning that the Mekhitarist erudite father Nersēs Akinian, whose study on Eremia Celebi's life and literary production provides a lot of useful information, discovered an autograph 144-page manuscript containing a not yet known literary work by Eremia himself, and namely the *Novel to Abro Celebi*. In the ending colophon, Eremia states that he composed the *Novel* between 1666 and 1672 as a token of gratitude for his own patron and adoptive father, Ambakum Eginli, one of the wealthiest Armenian businessmen in the seventeenth century Constantinople. In 1930, Akinian had come across Eremia's autograph manuscript of the *Novel* at the antiquarian bookshop of Ludwig Rosenthal in Munich, where the manuscript was for sale at a price of 550 Reichsmark (something like 2.600 euro nowadays). From the notes that Akinian precipitously wrote down during his visit to Rosenthal's bookstore I found close similarities between the content of what Akinian defines as the third tome of the *Novel* and the first section of the Venetian manuscript containing the *Polihistoriae*. Both texts deal in fact with churches that undergo destruction or underwent negotiations between different Christian communities through the mediation of local or central authorities. Unfortunately, the manuscript of the *Novel* has not yet come down to us, as very recently historian Gayane Ayvazyan shows in her study of the extant works by Eremia Celebi: G. Ayvazyan, “Eremia Čelepi K'yomurčyanij jeğrakakan žařangut'yunđ” [The manuscript legacy of Eremia Celebi K'ēōmiwřcean], *Banber Matendarani* 20/2014, pp. 349–388. Further research on Eremia's literary legacy is needed to establish his writing and publishing strategies as well as the intertextual correspondences between the *Polihistoriae*, the *Diary* and other fragmentary or incomplete historiographic works penned by Eremia.

12 While the *Vision of St. Nersēs* leaves room for hope in a revival of Armenian kingship (which happened with the Ārubineank' in Mediterranean Armenia), Eremia's eschatological understanding of St. Nersēs' curse is quite different, for, at the time of K'ēōmiwřcean, there was no longer hope for the restoration of a new Armenian royal dynasty. Indeed, in manuscript V509, f. 25r., we read as follows: Երկրորդ հատոր որպէս խօստացաք գրել յետ քանդման աներման եւ խափանման սուրբ եկեղեցեացն՝ մանաւանդ թէ սփռեալ

is a twelfth-century interpolation into the tenth-century *Life of St. Nersēs*, still exerted great influence on the seventeenth century Armenian self-perception and self-telling of ‘national’ catastrophes and disasters.¹³ Although they differ in terms of narrative structure and objectives, the *Polihistoriae* and the *Diary* are complementary works that shed light on seventeenth century Ottoman Turkish, Greek, Arabic, Jewish and Armenian social macro- and microhistory. They also provide insight on the seventeenth-century Armenian author’s and his own community’s (inter)subjectivity.¹⁴

2 First Case Study. Legitimizing the (Christian) Self through Sacred Biographies

The first case study illustrates one of the tendencies that defined the process of self-representation and self-legitimization of Armenians living in the seventeenth century Ottoman Empire. I argue that specific seventeenth century Armenian written texts were meant to provide Armenian Christian readers, especially of the eastern Anatolian provinces, with patterns of behaviour and faith that were inspired to the ascetic ideals and models of the Egyptian and Syriac Desert Fathers and were meant to legitimize the Christian self against the Muslim Other. Historically, this tendency to create community-building

առաջի աչաց մերոց՝ մեռնիա եւ իճամի առնէին իւրեանց . ըստ բանից մարգարէից եւ հայրապետին ներսէսի . թէ Օսարք կերիցեն զվաստակս ձեր առաջի աչաց ձերոց: Եւ արդ պատշաճ այն թէ (unreadable) ձեր անբակ եւ երկիրն ձեր հըրձիզք: [*<Here>* the second volume, in which we promised to write about the destruction, ruination and annihilation of the holy churches, especially those cases in which they converted *<the churches>* into mosques and schools under our eyes, according to the words of the Prophets and of Patriarch Nersēs that ‘Foreigners will consume your earning under your eyes. Thus, it is proper that (unreadable) your ruins and land were burned’].

13 For a detailed analysis of the historical context of the *Vision of St. Nersēs* and its eschatological features: Z. Pogossian, “The Last Emperor or the Last Armenian King? Some Considerations on Armenian Apocalyptic Literature from the Cilician Period”, in: *The Armenian Apocalyptic Tradition: A Comparative Perspective (Studia in Veteris Testamenti Pseudepigrapha Series 25)*, edited by K. Bardakjian & S. La Porta, Brill: Leiden, 2014, pp. 457–503.

14 These two terms are circumstantially used in the light of the general conceptual framework elaborated by Alfred Schütz and Thomas Luckmann in *The Structures of the Life-World [Strukturen der Lebenswelt]*, Volume 1, English Translation by R.M. Zaner & H.T. Engelhardt Jr., Northwestern University Press: Evanston 1973, pp. 4–5. On the relationship between the *Diary* and the *Polihistoriae*, cf. P. Ivanova, “Armenians in Urban Order and Disorder of Seventeenth-Century Istanbul”, *Journal of Ottoman and Turkish Studies Association* 4/2 (2017), pp. 239–260: 245.

metanarratives portraying early Christian asceticism as an exemplary golden age one can recreate elsewhere, was initiated by the Pahlawuni dynasty in the eleventh-twelfth century Mediterranean Armenia (Cilicia Armenia) for the purpose of reviving and reformulating the fourth-century Egyptian and Syriac ascetic ideal in tune with the contemporary challenges of their own Armenian community and of other 'confessional' communities of the East Christian oikumene.¹⁵ In this vein, seventeenth century authors, too, tried to reinvigorate the Pahlawuni's enterprise in building a shared sense of community belonging through the creation of strong connections between the idealized and golden age of early Christianity and their own contemporary troublesome present, in which the Christians of the east Mediterranean were confronted by sustained Islamization. In this respect, Grigor Daranac'is *Chronicle* offers indeed a fascinating literary witness to the longstanding and influential effects of the Pahlawuni's literary project on Armenian society, culture and mentality. In the second part of his work, Grigor dedicates several chapters to recount the life and activities of renown *vardapets* (hieromonks) of the Armenian church. By relying on late ancient and medieval Armenian practices of collecting and storing stories and sayings attributed to Greek and Syriac Desert fathers and mothers and to Armenian Church fathers – but also to Greek pagan philosophers –, Grigor portrays the liveliness of the sacred landscape of his native region, Ekeleac' (Upper Greater Armenia, roughly corresponding to the today's Erzincan province), by establishing a strong connection between Christian Armenian settlers and their inhabited geographical environment. In this region, which was associated with the Arsacid dynasty and St. Gregory the Illuminator by late ancient and medieval Armenian historical sources, there was such a tremendous concentration of Armenian monasteries that the Ottoman tax collectors of the sixteenth century designated one valley northwest of Kemah (Ani-Kamax) as Valley of Monasteries.¹⁶ Grigor recounts the stories of various influential ascetic and ecclesiastical personalities, whose strict lifestyles and powerful preaching displayed an example of virtue for their own target audience, who were most likely the inhabitants of the Ekeleac' region, whether they were villagers or citizens. A long chapter is dedicated to several notable figures from Erzinka/Erzincan, emphasising the continuous relationship and intense interaction between the "blessed" past and the present

15 I owe my colleague Samvel Grigoryan the use of the denomination 'Mediterranean Armenia' for Cilician Armenia: S. Grigoryan, *Les Arméniens et les Francs: étude historique et géographique de la noblesse et de son implantation dans l'Arménie méditerranéenne*, Thèse de doctorat, Université Paul Valéry Montpellier III 11 Décembre 2021.

16 Shapiro, *The Rise*, p. 39.

through the presence of specific sacred objects that shaped the city's space of devotion and piety. Churches and shrines on mount Sepuh and in the neighbourhoods of Erzinka are described as physical instantiations of the sacredness of the past. Grigor attributes their supernatural power and effectiveness to the 'trans-temporal' and metaphysical presence of St Gregory the Illuminator and of the first Christian king of Armenia, the Arsacid Trdat. When mentioning the life and literary activity of the renowned thirteenth-century theologian and rhetor Yovhannēs Erzknac'i, Grigor emphasises the significance of the spatial environment that enabled Yovhannēs' to develop his stunning literary activity:

All these <texts> were written in the monastery [i.e., of Saint Minas] for its safety, as was Nersēs the Great of Roman Klay, who wrote all his odes and hymns, as well as the worthy and marvellous song, called 'Jesus the Son', which is similar to the ode of Solomon called 'Song of Songs', and the 'Remember' and 'Be awake!' for the fortress guardians, and many other prayers and comments. All of this was created because of the safety and tranquillity of the place. As it is said, "The saint needs a holy house and purification <needs> a pure place" in order to become theologian and rhetorician. May their memory be blessed and may Christ our God have compassion on the believers and on us through the intercession of their prayers, amen!¹⁷

Grigor informs us that the monastery of Saint Minas, located on the slopes of mount Sepuh in Erzinka, possessed supernatural qualities due to the continuous and trans-temporal presence of the Illuminator and his offspring. This presence blessed the monastery with exceptional energy conducive to spiritual and intellectual growth.

Even though Daranac'i is primarily interested in celebrating the achievements of his contemporaries, he also reports on the deceptions of false

17 Grigor Daran Ի ci *Chronicle* (Jerusalem 1915, 4 օ– 1 Զայս ամենայն ի Սուրբ Մինաս անապատին է գրեալ վասն ապահովութեան տեղոյն, որպէս մեծ Շնորհալի Ներսէս Կլային հռովմական գրեալ է զամենայն երգն շարականաց եւ զձայնատուրաց եւ զհրաշալի պատուական երգն՝ զՅիսուս Որդի անուանեալ, որ հանգոյն է երգոյն Սողոմոնի, այն որ Երզնգ Երզ անուանի եւ զՅիշեացոյքն եւ զԶարթիքն՝ վասն պահողաց գրերդն եւ այլ բազում բանս աղօթականս եւ մեկնութիւնս: Զայս ամենայն վասն անքոյթ եւ խաղաղ տեղոյն է արարեալ, որպէս ասացեալ է թէ՛ Պարտ է սրբոյն սուրբ բնակարան, եւ մաքրելոյն մաքրուր կայան, ապա լինել աստուածաբան եւ անճադիցն վիպասան: Որոց յիշատակն օրհնութեան եղիցի եւ աղօթիւք նոցա Քրիստոս Աստուածն մեր հաասացելոցն եւ մեզ ողորմեսցի, ամէն: Unless otherwise stated, all translation are mine.

hieromonks and pseudo-ascetics who exploited many peasants and citizens for their own vainglory or profit.¹⁸ It seems to me that Grigor's strategy to locate narratives of fraudulent spiritual gurus and 'false prophets' after the narration of the deeds of virtuous and holy men intends to create a counter-narrative to his circumstantial core story for the purpose of celebrating and magnifying the morally excellent example of Armenian holy and virtuous men, by decrying the immoral and unlawful behaviour of the portrayed characters. Grigor's approach to his own 'hagiographic' material differs slightly from that of the Pahlawunis', which was aimed at reintroducing and domesticating stories of Egyptian and Syriac ascetics and Greek saints from the early Christian period to the Armenian imaginary. Grigor indeed performs an interesting operation: first, he offers a retrospective look at the geo-cultural context in which the activities of holy men of the past originated and then, he highlights that exceptional concentration of holiness in his own time. At the end of the Jerusalem edition of Grigor's *Chronicle*, we read the colophon (*yišatakaran*, lit. 'place of memory') penned by Grigor himself and contained in the Jerusalem manuscript 175 – a codex dating to 1610 and containing the *Lives and Sayings of the Desert Fathers (Apophtegmata Patrum)*. The colophon was penned by Grigor in honour of his teacher and mentor, Baron Mahdasi Čknawor (Paron Mahtasi Čgnawor), who himself copied the manuscript in Jerusalem. Grigor added the colophon in Jerusalem, most likely shortly after the compilation of the codex in 1610.¹⁹ The colophon is remarkable for its unique content, providing the reader with the biography of Baron Mahdasi Čknawor, a charismatic ascetic who decided to spend his entire life in the natural caves near Kemah as hermit following in the footsteps of St. Anthony the Great, Macarius of Rome and other ascetics whose instructions were carefully copied by Baron Čknawor in

18 Shapiro discusses Grigor's account of several Armenian villagers, deacons and heretics who deceived their fellow villagers, in particular women, by fashioning themselves as false and treacherous hieromonks and prophets: H. Shapiro, "Grigor Daranalc'i: An Armenian Chronicler of Early Modern Mass Mobility", in Krstić & Terzioğlu (eds.), *Entangled*, pp. 139–157.

19 The editor of the Grand Catalogue of Manuscripts of the Armenian Patriarchate in Jerusalem reports the Armenian year ԹԼԸ (corresponding to year 1587/9 of the Gregorian calendar) as year of composition of the colophon. However, Grigor was between 11 and 13 years old at that time. It is quite unlikely that Grigor did it as he met the ascetic Baron first in 1590. Furthermore, Bogharian reports that the manuscript was compiled by Baron Mahdasi in 1610, supposing thereby that the colophon of the manuscript was written some decades before the production of the manuscript itself. *Mayr C'uc'ak Jeragrac' srhoc' Yakobeanc': Hator arajin* [Grand Catalogue of St. James Manuscripts. Volume 1], edited by Bishop Norayr Bogharian, Armenian Convent Printing Press: Jerusalem, 1966, p. 526.

occasion of his pilgrimage to Jerusalem.²⁰ The singular hermit contributed to draw Grigor's attention towards the example of the Egyptian Desert fathers and to exert influence on the literary choices of the seventeenth century historian whose *Chronicle* is interspersed with narratives of past and contemporary ascetic figures.

3 Second Case-Study. Bargaining with the Sultan: Inter-communal and Inter-religious Conflicts around Devotional Spaces

The second case study is based on literary sources which attest to an increase in intra-Armenian and inter-Christian communal conflicts and dissension relating to the use of specific devotional spaces. Grigor's account of numerous instances of rebuilding and/or destruction of churches, as well as negotiations over control of church spaces (and of course, endowments), demonstrates the importance of church buildings in public and political spaces, both within specific communities and in the eyes of local and central Ottoman authorities. Apart from its significance at a micro-historical level, the narrative of how the administration of church buildings was integrated into the social and political urban landscape provides a lot of useful information on how social and institutional borders were constructed or deconstructed between different religious and confessional identities. It also enables us to understand the connections between faith communities ("Glaubensgemeinschaft") and devotional/sacred spaces, and the strategies employed by individuals, groups, and institutions to legitimise their authority among their coreligionists and the supra-communal powers. Several passages in Grigor's *Chronicle* report skirmishes between Armenians and Greeks following imperial decrees that permitted either group to use a church that had originally belonged to the other. Drawing on his experience as the Armenian bishop of Rodosto (nowadays, Tekirdağ), Grigor recounts the events surrounding the destruction of the first Armenian church in the city by the Turks in retaliation for an agreement between Greeks and Armenians following the abduction of a Greek youth by a certain Turkish sergeant in 1629. Interestingly, the initial accord between the native Greek population of Rodosto and the newly arrived Armenians dramatically turned into conflict when the Ottoman authorities decided to compensate the loss of the church building, which they themselves had caused, by bestowing the use of a Greek church upon the Rodosto Armenian community. This decision

20 English translation of some passages of the colophon in: Shapiro, *The Rise*, pp. 150–152.

inflamed the Rodosto Greek community, sparking riots between the city's two Christian groups.²¹

In his *Diary* and in his *Polihistoriae*, Eremia K'ēōmiwrčean recounts a wide range of incidents relating to the destruction of Armenian churches or to their conversion into mosques, for example in Amida and Erzurum, as well as to intercommunal conflicts and clashes concerning the ownership and control of church buildings, especially in Palestine. Among the variety of cases, it is worth mentioning that of the destruction of the Church of Saint Sargis in Bursa as it is told by Eremia at the very beginning of his *Polihistoriae*, according to the unpublished manuscript V509.

When a certain one of *hoja* offspring became the judge of Bursa and moved there, he became corrupt and a great enemy of the Christians. One day, he summoned the religious and wise men of the city and announced his intentions <what he had in mind> to all the Turkish townspeople. Then, riding a horse, he led them to the church of the Armenians, pulled it down from the roof to the basement with hatchets and hammers, destroying all <her> vessels and ornaments. The church was called *Kilisa Tēlisi*. He had planned to commit the same crime against the Greeks, but in the meantime, he heard that the Armenians had complained to vizir Kara Mustafa in Stampōl, and the latter relented when he heard about the destruction. (Blank space) Certain Armenians came to Mustafa Pasha by boat (blank space) and claimed so: 'We inherited our church from our ancestors as the main place of prayer for your kingdom's life. The judge committed it [this felony] without your order. But you are the righteous vizir of the king, and we demand your arbitration.'²²

21 Detailed discussion of this event is provided in: Shapiro, *The Rise*, pp. 91–93.

22 Ms. V509, f. 4r: Հօճազատէ ոմն դատի եղեալ պրոսայտո՛ երբ գնաց անդ շար թասուսայ եւ քրիստոնէաց յոյժ թշնամի. յաւոր միում կոչեալ զօսիթայս եւ զդանշմանս քաղաքին եւ մունէտկաւ զամենայն քաղաքացի տաճիկս եւ անկաւ առաջի նոցա ձիով առաջնորդ ամենեցուն, կացնօք եւ մրճօք հասին ի վերայ եկեղեցւոյն հայոց, եւ սկսան ի քակել ի տանեաց մինչ ի հիմունսն եւ աւար առին զամենայն անօթս եւ զսպասս. եւ կոչեցաւ անուն նորա քիլիսա տէլիսի: Եւ զայս նենգութիւնս մինչ կամէր հոռոնց եւս առնել՝ լուս թէ ի հայոց զանկատատորք սրլացան առ վիզիր զարա մուստաֆայ ի ստամպօլ վասն որոյ եւ թուլացաւ զի լուիցէ զկոտորածն: (Blank space) Հայք ոմանք զան առ մուստաֆ պաշայ առ նաւուտ (blank space) եւ գրեն զգանկատ թէ ի նախնեաց ունէաք զեկեղեցին մեր՝ եւ ոայս աղօթօղ վասն կենաց ձեր թագաւորութեանդ՝ վնասն ինչէր զի դատին առանց հրամանի ձեր զայս արար. թագաւորին ատիլ վէզիրն եւ դատաստան խնդրեմք ի քէն.

This long quote tells us that the Bursa Armenians were enough influential to urge a prompt reaction of minister Kara Mustafa (1634–83), who, having verified the reliability of Bursa Armenians' complaints, asked a *fatwa* (in Armenian, *fēt'va*) by the Grand Mufti and a *hatt-i sharif* (in Armenian, *xēt'i šerif*) by the Sultan to publicly punish the villain mullah of the city. After his public condemnation, the Bursa mullah was involved in a conspiracy organized by Siyavuş Pasha against Sultan Mehmed IV, which was however uncovered and punished with the exile of the mullah himself from Bursa. At the end of his account, Eremia states that he considers the exile of the Bursa judge to be a great miracle that compensated for the unjust loss of the Kilisa Tēlisi church and made it clear to «the great enemy of the holy faith of Christ our God» that the exile was a curse from the church herself. In his *Diary*, Eremia provides a shorter account of the event, offering details on the precise date and the perpetrator of the crime against the Bursa Armenians and their church. According to this brief account, the Armenian church in Bursa was pillaged and destroyed during the office of Kara Mustafa Pasha's tenure as vizier, at some point before 12 August 1651, by a man named Burnaz/Burnad, who was the son of a high-ranking official. Eremia also adds that this Burnaz/Burnad received a military appointment in Anatolia from Siyavuş Pasha the Elder (in officio as chief-minister, 1651–6) in recognition of his involvement in the destruction of the Armenian church in Bursa.²³

23 *Oragrut'wn Eremia Čelēpi K'ēōmiwrčeani* [Diary by Eremia Čelēpi K'ēōmiwrčean], edited by Mersop Arch. Nšanian, Tparan Srboc' Yakobeanč': Erusałēm, 1939, p. 21: Եւ հասանեալ ամբոխն վեզիրին եւ որք գտան անդ ի դագիցն՝ դագի էսքեր արար (պարսապ) եւ գՊոռնագ Հօճա գատէն՝ Ի Պուրսայոյ մանգոյ ի ժամանակէ կարա Մուստաֆին՝ վասն քակելոյ զեկեղեցին Հայոց ի Պրոռուսայ, գնայ Անատոլի Դագի էսքեր արար: Եւ սպան զորս եւ կամէր. նախ զթախլիսնի թագաւորին, եւ զՄէլէկն արսորեաց իրայնօրն հանդերձ. այս եղև Օգոստոս ամսոյ ԺԱ-ն ՌԴԹ=1651. [Thus, as the vizir (i.e., Abaza Siyavuş Pasha) pleased the crowd and those who were there among the *ghazi* (lit. victorious; it was a title conferred on exemplary Muslim warriors), he made chief of the Islamic fighters (blank, lacking) and Burnaz of *hoja* offspring, who was cast out of Bursa from the time of Kara Mustafa because of the destruction of the Armenian church in Bursa, he made him chief of the warriors in Anatolia. And this one murdered everyone whom he wished <to murder>: first, the *t'axlisči* [?] of the Sultan (lit., king), and then he exiled Melek (Ahmed Pasha) with all his siblings. This happened in the month of August 12, year 1651].

Eremia's narration is ordered per years according to the Armenian calendar, which traditionally uses the Armenian alphabet's letters to define the numerals. The editor of the *Diary* reports that the events of this section happened in 1650 without considering that the correspondence between the Armenian calendar and both the solar year and the Julian calendar slowly drifts over time, shifting across a year of the Julian calendar once in 1461 calendar years. Thus, starting from year 1461 of the Armenian calendar, one year must be added when calculating the corresponding one in the Julian calendar. The

Interestingly, Eremia reports that Kösem Mahpeyker Sultan, the mother of Sultans Murad IV and Ibrahim and grandmother of Sultan Mehmed IV, was assassinated on 22 August 1651 in collusion with Siyavuş Pasha himself. It is worth mentioning that scholarship generally attributes the assassination of Büyük Valide Kösem to her daughter-in-law, Turhan Hatice Sultan, and her entourage, but does not provide details on its members. Eremia's historiographical works are therefore useful and fundamental sources for reconstructing obscure and turbulent periods of Ottoman political and diplomatic history alongside with contemporary Ottoman Turkish sources.

In the abovementioned lengthy quotation from Eremia's *Polihistoriae*, Kara Mustafa is referred to as a vizier. We can infer that the Armenians asked him to intercede on their behalf, given his influence over the affairs of the Bursa area. We may also argue that Eremia disremembered the name, confusing Kara Mustafa, who was appointed grand vizier later in 1661, with Kara Murad Pasha, who was grand vizier between 21 May 1649 and 5 August 1650, and then again for a while in 1655. However, as the name of Kara Mustafa also appears in the *Diary*, it is highly unlikely that there was a repeated imprecision. It may therefore be inferred that, at the time of the destruction of the Armenian church in Bursa in 1651, Kara Mustafa was a senior official, before being elevated to the rank of chief minister some decades later.

4 Third Case Study. Breaking Down Religious Diversity: Amicable Relations and Intergroup Marriages

The third study case used in this contribution comes from a vignette that we read in Grigor Daranagc'i's *Chronicle*. The episode he describes provides compelling insights into the inner dynamics of coexistence and conflict between the Greeks and the Armenians of Rodosto through accounts of intercommunal love affairs. It offers a microscopic, domestic perspective on the disputes and rivalries between the two Ottoman Christian groups at a macroscopic level. Daranagc'i's account of a love affair between people of two different Christian denominations was later expanded by Eremia Celebi. By adopting the style and content of his predecessor, Eremia also sought to depict the intricate relationship between various religious groups in his contemporary political and social context through the lens of emotions and personal stories. However, in comparison to Grigor, Eremia Celebi goes further and provides a verse narrative

year ՔԼԵՒ' corresponds therefore to 1651 and not to 1650 as we read in Nšanian's edition of Eremia's *Diary*.

of the 'dangerous' relation between a Jewish girl and an Albanian boy of the Greek Orthodox faith, her willing conversion to Christianity, their marriage and the subsequent distress of her family and the entire Constantinopolitan Jewish community. The story known as *The Jewish Bride*, was first composed in Armenian and then in Armeno-Turkish. It was most likely intended for performance in the coffeehouses of the Ottoman capital to entertain an audience more willing to cross – or even break down – the traditional interfaith and inter-millet barriers between different religious and ethnic communities than the contemporary political and social climate in the Ottoman empire (and beyond) would suggest.²⁴ The literary trope of interfaith and interethnic love affairs and marriages was not unfamiliar to the Armenians, as it originated in the story of Yovhannēs and 'Aisha, which is attributed to Yovhannēs Erznkac'i by tradition.²⁵ The plot exerted such a seductive, powerful and unconventional charm that rapidly became very popular in Armenian oral vernacular literary culture (and most likely also among other local groups of the Anatolian countryside). Though problematic, discomfortable and challenging for the communities involved in the process, successful interfaith marriages show that a certain level of accommodation and friendship allowed different individuals and groups of the Ottoman social landscape to go beyond either hostility or conventional tolerance.²⁶ Stories on inter-millet and interfaith sexual relationship or friendship also served as a kind of toolbox for deconstructing prejudice and conflict by purposely choosing of representing the other through unconventional parameters, those of feelings and emotions. It comes as no surprise that Eremia rendered the late medieval Armenian translation of the renown Provençal romance *Paris et Vienne* into Armeno-Turkish for the delight of his co-fellow readers as explicitly stated by the author himself in the incipit of his translation. Once again, Eremia tells the story of problematic lovers who, through their union, sought to challenge traditional social hierarchies, prompting their readers and audience to question long-standing and static categories of identity and belonging. Another intriguing question concerns

24 *Eremya Chelebi Kōmürjian's Armeno-Turkish poem The Jewish Bride*, edited and translated by A. Sanjian & A. Tietze, Otto Harrassowitz: Wiesbaden, 1981. For an overview of Eremia's literary activity: K.B. Bardakjian, *A Reference Guide to Modern Armenian Literature, 1500–1920 with an Introductory History*, Wayne State University Press: Detroit, 2000, pp. 59–63.

25 Beautifully discussed in: M. Pifer, *Kindred Voices. A Literary History of Medieval Anatolia*, Yale University Press: New Heaven & London, 2021, pp. 201–9.

26 In a comparative perspective, it is worth mentioning this valuable study: D. Jütte, "Interfaith Encounters between Jews and Christians in the Early Modern Period and Beyond: Toward a Framework", *American Historical Review* 2013, pp. 378–400.

the relationship between the varying levels of interest in this provocative literary genre of Yovhannēs Erznkac'ī, Grigor Daranałc'ī and Eremia Celebi and their own geographical origins. All three authors hailed from either the city of Erznka or the nearby village of Kemah. Yovhannēs was certainly inspired by the thirteenth-century multicultural and cosmopolitan city of Erznka, which facilitated intellectual, cultural and social interconnections and interchanges between Christian Armenians and Muslims. This specific cultural and social environment influenced Armenian mentality and *Weltanschauung* in this area (as well as in other eastern Ottoman Armenian regions, such as the region of Van and its surroundings), differentiating the Armenians of the eastern regions from those in the western regions of the Ottoman Empire. Further research is needed to assess and map how Armenian authors living in cosmopolitan ambiances across pre-Ottoman and Ottoman *Rūm* and the Armenian highlands tell emotions. For the time being, our analysis will focus on Grigor's narration of the love affair between two members of two different Christian communities living in the same city, the reaction mechanisms of both communities and of the strategies employed by the Muslim Turkish community to exploit Christian intercommunal disorders.

Grigor himself was involved in the Rodosto Armeno-Greek love affair, as he was serving as bishop of the Rodosto Armenian community at the time of the incident. From the outset of the narrative, Grigor does not disparage the Greek girl or her Armenian lad but makes the readers clear his veiled disapproval towards the local Greek community, which caused damages and troubles to her fellow believers.²⁷ When considered in its historical context, the account can also be interpreted as an indication of awareness and a circumstantial criticism of the on-going process of confession-building that not only divided Western Christendom, but also Eastern Christendom, exacerbating dormant quarrels and rivalries among various Christian denominations and groups in the East. Daranałc'ī describes the incident as follows:

On the 20th of December 1620, a certain youth from our nation who was carder by profession went to the house of some Greeks with bad intentions under the guise of looking for cotton. [There was there] one girl of tall stature, they loved each other and decided to marry in accordance with the girl's mother. Then they came to us to obtain the authorization to come to the church and marry. However, I did not allow them to come

27 In this vein, it is worth mentioning Nersēs Šnorhali Klayec'īs riddles slyly mocking the Greeks among others: Pifer, *Kindred Voices*, op. cit., p. 146.

to the church for the fear of deceitful and fraudulent peoples, and they went to their own house and got married.²⁸

Even though it is not clear if Grigor was directly involved in the domestic marriage,²⁹ the account shows that Grigor's position was not at all aligned with a traditional one, according to which institutional and social borders among communities of different faiths or denominations were to be kept. Grigor also points out that the Rodosto *Tačikk'*, i.e., the local Muslim Turks, took advantage of this embarrassing situation to mock the Greeks and brew troubles between the two Christian local communities for their own profits. The Rodosto Armenians were otherwise able to avoid dangerous consequences thanks to a good network of personal connections with an Armenian high-ranking official of the imperial court, a certain Xalifa Astwacatur, who enjoyed the favours of Sultan Osman II (1618–22). Grigor also describes the cruelties that the Greek girl suffered by her coreligionists, when she was abducted and delivered to the local Muslim kadi (qāđī) to be converted by force. Grigor is very accurate in reporting the words that the Greeks pronounced in front of the city judge, when publicly denouncing the girl as a community cheater and traitor. The Greeks cried out 'it is better that she is *tačik* than *yermani*'.³⁰ Grigor's eyewitness report unfolds indeed the deepest resentment and hostility of a Christian community towards a coreligionist one when the Christian minority out-group, i.e., the Armenian newcomers, entered the borders of the coreligionist majority in-group, i.e., the Rodosto Greeks, threatening the social balance between dominant and sub-dominant groups, i.e. Muslim Turks and Christian Greeks.

28 Grigor Daranalc'i, *Chronicle* (Jerusalem 1915), p. 201: Թվին Ռկ եւ Թ ի մնաւ եօթանասունին, ղեկտեմբեր ամսոյ քսանին, ի հնարից չարին ոմն երիտասարդ յազգէ մերմէ արուեստի հալած գնալով ի տունս հռոմոց ի պատճառս բամպակի. մէկ աղջիկ մեծահասակ կացեր միոյ, սիրով կու կապակցին ընդ միմեանս եւ ուխտ եղեալ առնուլ զմիմեանս կամօք մօր աղջկանն, եւ եկին առ մեզ ի հրաման առնուլ, զի բերեալ պասկեցեն յեկեղեցին. նա եւ հրաման չետու յեկեղեցին բերելոյ վասն ահից նենգաժոտ եւ խեղաթիւր ազգացն, այլ տարեալ յիւրեանց տունն պասկեցին: The episode is discussed by Henry Shapiro: Shapiro, *The Rise*, pp. 90–91.

29 At a first glance, the marriage may have been celebrated by Grigor himself but a more circumstantial and thorough examination of the manuscripts containing Grigor's *Chronicle* would be a desideratum to substantiate this hypothesis.

30 The term *tačik* refers to the Turks, whereas the term *yermani* means Armenian: Grigor Daranalc'i, *Chronicle* (Jerusalem 1915), pp. 203–204.

5 Contextualizing the Fourth Case Study: Latins and Armenians in Dialogue

Providing an overview of the historical context of interconfessional negotiations and encounters between Latins and Armenians in the late Byzantine and post-Byzantine periods can clarify the dynamics of the community-building process experienced by Ottoman Armenians in the early modern period. Furthermore, it sheds light on the historical background that influenced and shaped the doctrinal altercation between Latins and Armenians in the seventeenth century.

From the fourteenth century onwards, two main ecclesiological tendencies emerged within the Armenian Church as a result of the intense contacts and exchanges between Cilician Armenia and the Papacy in the twelfth and thirteenth centuries.

- 1) The first tendency was autocephalous, defining the complete independence of the Armenian Church from the Roman Catholic and Byzantine Eastern Churches, by relying on the first three ecumenical councils and rejecting the Council of Chalcedon.
- 2) The Uniate tendency (Uniatism) represented by the missionary movement of the *Fratres Unitores*, an Armenian branch of the Dominican order, who supported submission to the authority of Rome and the adoption of the Latin rite.³¹

These main trends produced offshoots, from which two additional tendencies emerged (although this categorization does not claim to describe or include every instance of encounter between different 'confessional' groups):

31 M.A. van den Oudenrijn, « Uniteurs et Dominicains d'Arménie: l'union de Qrnay (1330) », *Oriens Christianus* 40 (1956), pp. 94–112; van den Oudenrijn, « Uniteurs et Dominicains d'Arménie: le nouvel athénée », *Oriens Christianus* 42 (1958), pp. 110–133; van den Oudenrijn, « Uniterus et Dominicanis d'Arménie: la Congregation des Uniteurs », *Oriens Christianus* 43 (1959), pp. 110–119; van den Oudenrijn, « Uniteurs et Dominicains d'Arménie: les adversaires de l'union », *Oriens Christianus* 45 (1961), pp. 95–108; van den Oudenrijn, « Uniteurs et Dominicains d'Arménie: les Dominicains de Naxiǰewan », *Oriens Christianus* 46 (1962), pp. 99–115; *Yovhannēs K'ṛnec'i. Yalags k'erakanin* [Yovhannēs K'ṛnec'i. On Grammar] edited by L.S. Xaç'ikyan & S.S. Avazyan, Erevan 1977, pp. 5–51; P. Lucca, «Cleansing the Christian Vineyard», pp. 39–62; S. La Porta, "Armeno-Latin Intellectual Exchange in the Fourteenth Century. Scholarly Traditions in Conversations and Competition", *Medieval Encounters* 21 (2015), pp. 269–294; C.A. Bonifacio, "Mixti cum Francis et Latinis. Ulteriori tasselli nella definizione dei rapporti tra Armeni e Latini agli inizi del XIV secolo", *Armenia, Caucaso e Asia Centrale Ricerche* 2022. *Eurasiatica* 19 (2022), a cura di D. Artoni, C. Frappi, P. Sorbello, pp. 37–53.

- 1) Those who accepted communion with Rome by adopting circumstantial liturgical and ritual modifications. Several former Armenian students of the *Collegio Urbanum* embraced this attitude.³²
- 2) Those who accepted the communion first with Byzantium and then with Rome, maintaining however the liturgical and canonical tradition of the Armenian church. In its essence, this attitude was developed by Catholicos Nersēs IV Klayec'i (*in officio*, 1166–73) and his successor, Grigor Tlay Pahlawuni (*in officio*, 1173–93).

Depending on the times and political circumstances, these tendencies and sub-tendencies co-existed and challenged each other. During the Cilician period, for example, all of the trends existed within the Armenian ecclesiastical and political elites. Two main factors were instrumental in the dramatic shift that characterized Armenian diplomacy in the Cilician period (from the mid-twelfth century until 1375). First, the Armenian political axis shifted from Byzantium to Western Europe and Rome, resulting in the development of pro-Latin Armenian Messianism, which viewed the Christian Latin world as the protector par excellence of Eastern Christianity.³³ The second factor was indeed the creation of a political axis between the West and several Muslim powers, such as the Seljūq Sultanate of Konya and the Mamluks. Here, the Armenians were the most favourable and powerful political partners of the Latin West due to their geographical, cultural and historical position between

32 In 1701, there was an attempt to conciliate the two parties involved in the religious and civil conflict that tore Catholic Armenians and Apostolic Armenians of Constantinople. The attempt was carried out by the Prior of the Capuchin missionaries in Constantinople, Fr. Hyacinthe-François, the ambassador of France De Feriol and Armenian vardapet Xaç'atur, who was the vicar of the Armenian Patriarch of Constantinople but also a supporter of *Propaganda Fide*. In the document that they submitted to both the S.C.P.F. and the Armenian Catholicos of Etchmiadzin, it was clearly mentioned the necessity of admitting non-Uniate Armenians to the Holy Communion (*communicatio in sacris*), as well as of dismissing the practice of anathemizing the council of Chalcedon and the pope Leo I in the Armenian liturgy. Further discussion in: M. Abagian, "La questione della *communicatio in sacris* nel secolo XVIII", *Bazmavēp* CXXI (1983), pp. 215–234, part. p. 228–9; *Santus, Transgressioni necessarie*.

33 A compelling example of Armeno-Cilician Messianism is the PSEUDO EPIPHANII, *Sermo de Antichristo* (Armeniaca de Fine Temporum), introduzione, testo critico, versione latina e note di G. FRASSON, Venezia – S. Lazzaro 1976. According to the scholar, the work dates to the twelfth century, perhaps to its first half (pp. XLII–LIV). On the apocalyptic literature of this period, it is worth mentioning the second part of the monumental volume: *The Armenian Apocalyptic Tradition*, edited by Kevork Bardakjian and Sergio La Porta, which focuses on this genre in the period between the eleventh and the fifteenth centuries.

East and West, and their status as Christians under the Caliphate.³⁴ Negotiations and dialogue with the Papacy were initiated by Catholicos Grigor Vkasasēr Pahlawuni (1065/66–1105), and developed further by Catholicos Grigoris III Pahlawuni (1113–66).³⁵ In the late Cilician period, a so-called ‘latinophile’ or ‘romanophile’ tendency emerged among the Armenian ecclesiastical high elite and aristocracy, including thereby King Het‘um II (r. 1289–1306 with interruptions) and Catholicos Grigor VII Anawarzec‘i (*in officio*, 1293–1307). In contrast, the early Cilician Armenian Church maintained a more balanced attitude. Catholicos Nersēs IV Klayec‘i, Catholicos Grigor IV Tlay Pahlawuni (*in officio*, 1173–93) and Archbishop Nersēs Lambronac‘i of Tarsus (1153–98), emphasized the importance of distinguishing between the substantial orthodoxy of the Greek and Armenian churches and their different dogmatic formulations in Greek and Armenian, resulting from semantic nuances between the two languages.³⁶ Nersēs Klayec‘i’s and Nersēs Lambronac‘i’s reflection on linguistic relativity in relation to theological and philosophical concepts was based on the awareness of the limitations of human thought and language when it came to expressing the mystery of the Incarnation. The legacy of Klayec‘i’s and Lambronac‘i’s approach to interconfessional dialogue continued through the

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- 34 B.L. Zekiyān, “The Iranian Oikumene and Armenia”, *Iran and the Caucasus* 9/2 (2005), pp. 231–256.
- 35 On Catholicos Grigoris II Vkasasēr (Martyrophile): A. Kapoian-Kouymjian, “Le catholicos Grégoire II le Martyrophile (Vkasasēr) et ses pérégrinations”, in *Bazmavap* CXXXII (1974), 316–8, repr. In: *L’Égypte vue par les Arméniens (XI^e–XVII^e siècles)*, edited by Kapoian-Kouymjian, Ed.s de la Fondation Singer-Polignac, Paris, 1988, pp. 13–14 (7–19).
- 36 Cf. B.L. Zekiyān, « Un dialogue œcuménique au XII^e siècle: les pourparlers entre le catholicos St. Nersēs Šnorhali et le légat impérial Théorianos en vue de l’union des Églises arménienne et byzantine », in: *Actes du XV^e Congrès International d’Études Byzantines – Athènes, Sept. 1976, IV, Histoire. Communications*, Athènes, 1980, pp. 420–441; repr. as: « St Nersēs Šnorhali en dialogue avec les Grecs: un prophète de l’œcuménisme au XII^e siècle », in: *Armenian Studies, Études Arméniennes in memoriam Haïg Berberian*, Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation: Lisboa, 1986, pp. 861–883; Zekiyān, « St. Nersēs de Lambron Docteur de l’Église Arménienne et théologien de l’union des Églises », *Jahrbuch der österreichischen Byzantinistik* 31/Beiheft, XVI. Internationaler Byzantinistenkongress. Akten, 1/Beiheft, Wien 1981, 2.1; Zekiyān, « Les relations arméno-byzantines après la mort de St. Nersēs Šnorhali », in: XVI. Internationaler Byzantinistenkongress. Akten 11/4, *Jahrbuch der österreichischen Byzantinistik* 32/4, 331–337; Zekiyān, “The Armenian Community of Philippopolis and the Bishop Ioannes Atmanos Imperial Legate to Cilicia”, in: *Between the Danube and the Caucasus. Oriental Sources on the History of the Peoples of Central and South-Eastern Europe*, Budapest, 1987, pp. 363–373; E. Suttner, “Eine ‘Ökumenische Bewegung’ im 12. Jahrhundert und ihr bedeutendster Theologe, der armenische Katholikos Nerses Schnorhali”, *Kleronomia* 7, 1 (1975), pp. 87–97; H. Khatchadourian, “The Christology of St. Nerses Schnorhali in Dialogue with Byzantium”, *Miscellanea Francescana* 78 (1978), pp. 413–434.

work of later Armenian Church patriarchs.³⁷ In the early seventeenth century, catholicos Movsēs Tat'ewac'i (1578–1632) displays a similar awareness in his epistles to pope Urbanus VIII, attempting to mediate between the Armenian Catholic archbishop of Naxĵewan and the Dominican missionary Paolo Piromalli.³⁸ By contrast, the attitude of *Propaganda Fide* and the latter were completely at odds with Nersēs Klayec'i's conceptualization of linguistic relativity, maintaining the unsuitability of the Armenian language and grammar for expressing theological subtleties that were 'orthodoxy' denoted by Latin.³⁹

6 Fourth Case Study. Strategies of Assimilation by Undermining Opposing Arguments

This article's final case study aims to compare the Armenian perception of Piromalli's preaching activities with his own use of dialectics to persuade and stigmatise his Armenian counterparts.

Grigor's *Chronicle* provides valuable insight into Piromalli's personality and his catechetical activities among the Armenians of Etchmiadzin, Constantinople, and Wallachia. This information is crucial for understanding how the Armenians reacted to the Dominican's behaviour and proselytization. Grigor portrays Piromalli as a dangerous, pernicious, and ambiguous person, claiming that he deceived several high-ranking Armenian ecclesiastics, including Catholicos Movsēs Tat'ewac'i (*in officio*, 1629–33) and Catholicos P'lippos Albakec'i (*in officio*, 1633–55), during his time in Armenia from 1631 to 1636.

37 Among others, it is worth mentioning the Cilician *catholicoi* Mxit'ar I (1341–1355) and Mesrop I (1359–1372). The latter restored, during the last council of Sis (1361), the practice of the ancient Armenian liturgical traditions and posed restrictions to the strong interference of the Latin church on the issues of ecclesiastical communion, rite, liturgy and spiritual traditions of the Armenian church: cf. M. Č'amč'ean, *Patmowt'iwn Hayoc' i skzbanē minjew* 1784, Venetik-S.Łazar 1784–1786, t. III, pp. 353–354, 358. Another ecclesiastic who showed a moderate attitude in interconfessional disputes was the Patriarch of Constantinople Yovhannēs Kolot (*in officio*, 1715–1741) who convinced Catholicos Karapet II (1726–1729) to abolish the practice of anathemising the council of Chalcedon and pope Leo I in the Armenian liturgy to enable the pro-Catholic Armenians to participate in the Latin Catholic liturgy: M. Abagian, "La questione della «communicatio in sacris» nel secolo XVIII e la formazione del Patriarcato armeno cattolico", in *Bazmavep* CXXXIX (1981), pp. 129–182: 135; Santus, *Trasgressioni necessarie*, pp. 366–367.

38 G. Amaduni, *Oskan Vardapet Erewanc'i ew ir žamanakð* [The Vardapet Oskan Erewanc'i and His Time], Venetik-S. Łazar, 1975, p. 268; N. Akinean, *Movsēs G. Tat'ewac'i Hayoc' Kat'olikosn ew ir žamanakð* [Movsēs III of Tat'ew, catholicos of the Armenians, and his time], Vienna-Mxit'arean Tparan, 1936, pp. 376–381.

39 Lucca, *From Doctrinal Persuasion to Economic*, pp. 477–478: footnote 111.

Grigor brands the Dominican preacher a *yizvit'* (i.e., Jesuit) and a heretic. According to the Armenian historian, Piromalli sought to indoctrinate the hieromonks and monks of Etchmiadzin with Catholic dogmas and to monopolize the education of young novices at the Etchmiadzin seminary in the absence of Catholicos P'lippos. From Grigor's account, it emerges that Piromalli must have possessed exceptional rhetorical and persuasive skills, even though our author obviously refrains from praising him for these capacities.⁴⁰ By describing Piromalli's preaching strategies, Grigor emphasizes that the Dominican convinced the young monks of Etchmiadzin that Armenian exegetical works were overly complicated compared to the Latin ones. Piromalli intended to elucidate the latter in a simple manner for the monks' spiritual and intellectual benefit. In this respect, Grigor remarks as follows:

[He explained them] not only the meaning [of the scriptures], but he introduced to them the evil heresies of Leo's Chalcedonian tomes, especially the novelties of the Frankish heresies (i.e., Latin), on which it is impossible to write, concerning the abjuration of the light (i.e., referring to the debate over the descent of the holy light in Jerusalem) and

40 It is worth mentioning the memories of the Capuchin missionary Gabriel de Chinon: *Relations du Levant. Perses, Arméniens et Gaures. Une aventure missionnaire au XVII^e siècle. Gabriel de Chinon (1610–1668)*. Introductions Jean-Pierre Mahé, Histoire à la Carte Éditeur 2020, p. 201: « Ce qu'a fait sur (plus que) tous les autres, et possible avec trop de zèle, un Dominicain, lequel, ayant appris la langue arménienne à Nakchivan, vint ici depuis environ douze ans, et durant le temps qu'il y a demeuré a poursuivi, et avec tant de chaleur, les vardapietes de Iulfa qu'ils ne l'oublieront jamais. Ce bon père, qui était en vérité doué d'un grand zèle et fort savant, eût sans doute fait davantage parmi eux, s'il eût su modérer son zèle, qu'il faut savoir faire paraître avec mesure et selon les occasions. Il les poursuivait à toute heure, jusque même dans la place publique, et aux jours de marché, qu'il les excommuniait, fulminant contre eux toutes sortes d'anathèmes. Je crois que sono zèle l'eût porté à continuer cet exercice, s'ils n'y eussent mis ordre, et comme les plus forts dans leur ville, l'obligèrent enfin de sortir, l'ayant plusieurs fois chassé à coups de pierre par les enfants que les vartapietes faisaient agir ». This long passage illustrates very well Piromalli's behavioural characteristics. Before this passage, Gabriel de Chinon reports the case of two Carmelites, who following Piromalli acquired such a knowledge of the Armenian language to be able to argue and discuss with the Armenians of Julfa, getting their sympathy and approval. Certainly, the Capuchin wanted to make his readers aware of the fact that, among the missionary orders in Persia and neighbouring areas, there were diverging approaches and strategies of arousing the sympathies of non-Catholic and non-Christian individuals and groups.

I would like to thank my colleague Giorgio Rota for drawing my attention to the memories of Gabriel de Chinon and providing me with the volume.

the establishing of the date of Easter and many other heresies that the Chalcedonians do not have, neither Greeks nor any other.⁴¹

Grigor's nasty tone targets the new reforms within the Catholic Latin Church rather than the Chalcedonians themselves. He seems to criticize some of the recent reforms introduced in the Roman Church, such as the replacement of the Julian calendar with the Gregorian calendar by Pope Gregory XIII in 1582, more than the council of Chalcedon by itself. Piromalli exerted such an irresistible fascination over many Armenian monks at Etchmiadzin that they decided to clothe him in the cowl and cloak of an Armenian monk and give him the *baculum*, traditionally held by Armenian hieromonks. They then made him sit down on the chair of the vardapets, thereby allowing him to instruct them and clarify the difficult writings of the early fifteenth-century Armenian scholastic philosopher and theologian Grigor Tat'ewac'i. The latter had directed the prominent and leading monastic school of Tat'ew in southern Armenia and had played a crucial role in protecting the Armenian Apostolic Church from the proselytizing activities of Dominican missionaries, who had enjoyed success among the Armenians of the Armenian highlands and eastern Anatolia since the beginning of the fourteenth century. We are told that, around 1636, Piromalli was finally expelled from Etchmiadzin, once Catholicos P'lippos realized the threat that the Dominican posed to his authority and to his flock. That same year, Piromalli moved to Constantinople, where he sought to preach the Armenians of Galata, achieving some success:

We were in the church of the Holy Bearer of God [in Galata], when the evil persuaded all the priests of Galata and their own flocks, especially our son Xoճա T'awit' and Kirakos Jułayec'i, by telling them: 'I spent three years in Etchmiadzin and became Armenian, I am disciple of P'lippos and I got the authority of the hieromonks (*vardapetakan išxanut'wn*) to preach'. And thereafter, they raised him to the chair, and he started to give sermons in Armenian on the history of the Illuminator to be first pleasant to the simple people.⁴²

41 Grigor Daranalc'i, *Chronicle* (Jerusalem 1915), p. 584: Ոչ թէ զիմաստն միայն, այլ զչարչար հերձուածսն քաղկեդոնական լեւոնական տումարիցն, մասաւանդ զվերջոյ նորոյ աղանդից ֆռանգացն, զոր չէ հնար գրելոյ, թէ վասն լուսոյ ուրանալոյն եւ վասն զատկաց որոշելոյն եւ այլ նոր հերձուածս բազումս, զոր քաղկեդոնիկք ոչ ունին՝ ոչ յոյնք եւ ոչ այլ որ:

42 Grigor Daranalc'i, *Chronicle* (Jerusalem 1915), p. 585: եւ մէք աստ պատահելով յայն ժամն, յԱստուածածին եկեղեցին լինելով, նա՛ այն չարն հաստացուցանելով զամենայն դալաթացի քահանայքն եւ դիրահասատն ժողովուրդքն, մասաւանդ զմեր որդեակն

In the aftermaths, two Armenian priests went to the Patriarch and asked him why Piromalli was allowed to preach to their own flock. The Patriarch's reply makes it clear that two lay Julfans, namely Xoĵa Tawit' (Dawit') and Kirakos Ĵulayec'i, were so powerful and influential within the community to bypass the Patriarch's authority in managing the communal affairs. On the Patriarch's initiative, Grigor himself and other priests were ordered to denounce Piromalli's deceptive preaching in front of the flock. Following heated public disputes between the two parties, the Dominican was forced to move to Poland, where he continued his missionary work among the local Armenian Catholic communities. We are then told that Piromalli persuaded the Armenian Catholic priests of Suceava to refrain from baptizing newborn Armenian children or anointing the dying, on account of his own authority over them as *catholicos*.⁴³ The inclusion of Piromalli's direct words into the third person standard narrative confirms that Grigor's account relies on eyewitness reports. The later involvement of Piromalli in the process of the Church Union of the Polish Armenians between 1638 and 1645 lacks in Grigor's account, which most likely ends just before 1638.

While Grigor is critical towards Piromalli, a close reading of the Dominican's *Apology* reveals a quite different facet of this controversial personality. The *Apology* was written in response to a faith confession of Armenian orthodoxy compiled by a certain Simon, an Armenian vardapet of Etchmiadzin, who apparently was in good terms with Piromalli as the latter calls him 'my dear'. Initially composed in Latin between the end of 1634 and the beginning of 1635 and then published in Vienna in 1656 together with the *De Fide catholica ad regem Persarum*, the *Apology* was rendered into Armenian most likely by the author himself, even though further research is needed to substantiate this hypothesis. According to Tisserant, ms. Borg Arm 40.2 should contain Piromalli's autograph that regrettably I was unable to find. By contrast, ms. Borg. Arm. 10 contains the Armenian version of the *Apology* in 301 ff. The text is made up of different sections, in which the Dominican deals with specific Christological and ecclesiastical issues and especially focuses on clarifying the Incarnation of the Second Person of the Trinity according to the orthodox faith, by interpreting a vast array of patristic authors. Piromalli also displays

զլԻճճայ Տաւիթն եւ զԿիրակոս Զուղայեցին, ասելով թէ՛ երեք ամ Էջմիածին կեցեալ եմ եւ հայ եմ եղեալ եւ աշակերտ եմ Փիլիպպոսին եւ վարդապետական իշխանութիւն եմ առաեալ քարոզելոյ: Եւ նորա զնա դասագլուխ կանգնեցնելով եւ սկսեալ հայ լեզու քարոզ ասել զպատմութիւն Լուսատրչին, զի նախ նովաւ հաւանեցուցէ զպարզամիտսն:

43 *Ibid.*, p. 588.

a good knowledge of Armenian Patristics and theological literature, quoting, for instance, from Patriarch Proclus' *Letter to the Armenians* and the Armenian homiliaries. In terms of rhetorical devices, the Dominican appeals to a long Chalcedonian tradition of heresiological *topoi*, by alleging that the Armenians maintain one nature and deny therefore either the human or the divine nature of Christ. Interestingly, he combines Christological and anthropological discussions, by tackling the question of the status of the body of Christ.⁴⁴ The issue of the incorruptibility or corruptibility of the body of Christ is one of the main arguments used by Piromalli to show, in his intent, the distortion of Armenian faith. It is worth quoting a passage from this chapter entitled 'Reply on the Logos, the One Incarnated Nature of the Logos and its meaning':

Let us declare according to the Armenian vardapets that by saying one nature it is meant unity and not duality, for duality hampers unity and the other way around, unity duality. Thus, those who affirm that, after the union, divinity and humanity became one nature, they are unable to distinguish either of them in the one after their union. And they are even unable to distinguish whether the one became in one or the other (of the natures), or whether it became not in one but in the other or not in a certain but in another one, or not in this but in that one. And they cannot say if the one is in the divinity or in the humanity and if it is according to the divinity or to the humanity, for once the two became one, the duality was removed because of the union into one nature. And at that moment the number two was abolished by unity into <the number> one. As unity is abolished and hindered by division in two, similarly duality is hindered by union into one nature. Even though two natures are united into one nature, they are no more two and it is not possible to say that they are two, for they became one.⁴⁵

44 In the history of Greek Chalcedonian polemics against non-Chalcedonians, and especially Armenians, the issue of the corruptibility or incorruptibility of the body of Christ appears in the eleventh century in connection to the Christological problem of the nature of the incarnated Son: T. Kolbaba, "East Roman Anti-Armenian Polemic Ninth to Eleventh Centuries", *Journal of Orthodox Christian Studies* 3/2 (2020), pp. 121–73: 158–159. For a recent discussion of the problem: B. Contin, "Whoever Eats My Flesh and Drinks My Blood Remains in Me, and I in Him' (John 6:56–57): Theoretical Developments in Understanding the Mystery of the Eucharist in Medieval Armenian Theology, in: *The Metaphysics and Theology of the Eucharist*, edited by G. Klima (Historical-Analytical Studies on Nature, Mind, and Action 10), Springer Nature: Switzerland AG, 2023, pp. 67–85.

45 Ms. Borg. Arm 10, f. 16v.–17r.: Յայտարարինք եւ ըստ Հայոց վարդապետաց թէ մի բնութիւն ասելն նշանակէ զմիութիւն եւ ոչ զերկուութիւն. զի երկուութիւն խափանէ զմիութիւն եւ զընդդէմ միութիւն զերկուութիւն. ապա որք ասեն զաստուածութիւն

Piromalli's approach to Christological problems is the standard one of the Greek late medieval polemic, while late medieval Latin literature against Armenians was more concerned with liturgical and orthopraxis-related issues than with dogmatical and theological questions.⁴⁶ His rhetorical approach is however refined and subtle, as he exploits a very philosophically informed way of developing his reasoning by means of confutation and *reductio ad absurdum* with the purpose of compelling his adversary to recognize the absurdity of his initial statement through the negation of the latter via reasoning and demonstration. In arguing his viewpoint, Piromalli's tone is never vituperative and nasty, but his viewpoint is otherwise openly critical. By relying on a Chalcedonian two-nature theology, the Dominican insinuates that the one-nature Christology of the Armenians denies the reality of Christ's body and implies not only its incorruptibility but also Christ's one will and energy in contrast with the position of the Roman Catholic Church. The problem of Christ's energy and will was one of the most delicate and controversial questions among Chalcedonian and non-Chalcedonian eastern Christians since the sixth century CE and became a heated question in Armenian theology and apologetics only from the end of the seventh and the beginning of the eighth century to be then almost completely dismissed in the twelfth century ecclesiastical negotiations between the Greek and the Armenian Churches.⁴⁷ In his extensive argument in favour of the two incarnate natures of the Word, it is worth mentioning that Piromalli alleges a fallacy in the ancient Armenian translation of Cyril of Alexandria's writings. He assumes that the Armenian dogma of the one incarnate nature of the Word depends on a translation error.

եւ գմարդկութիւն յետ միաւորութեան մի եղեալ բնութիւն. այլ ոչ կարեն յետ միաւորութեան յերկուս զանազանել զմինն այն, այլ ոչ կարեն զանազանել զմինն եղեալ ի յայլ եւ յայլ բնութիւն. եւ ոչ ի մի եւ միսն. եւ ոչ յոմն եւ յոմն բնութիւն, ոչ յայս եւ յայն: Ապա ոչ կարեն ասել ի յաստուածութիւն եւ ի մարդկութիւն. կամ ըստ աստուածութեան եւ ըստ մարդկութեան. վասն զի յորժամ երկուքն մի եղեւ երկուքիւն բարձաւ ի ձեռն միաւորութեան ի մի բնութիւն. եւ յայնժամ երկոցն թի խափանեցաւ միաւորութեամբ ի մի: Զի որպէս միութիւն ի ձեռն անջատմանն ի յերկուս բառնի եւ խափանի. նոյնպէս երկուքիւն ի ձեռն միաւորութեան ի մի բնութիւն, խափանի. եւ մինչեւ երկուքն բնութիւնքն միաւորեալ են ի մի բնութիւն. երկու ոչ են. եւ ոչ կարեն զերկուս ասել գնոսս, զի մի եղեւն: Իսկ եթէ զերկուս անուանեն, զմիութիւնն խափանեցին:

- 46 P. Halfter, *Das Papsttum und die Armenier im frühen und hohen Mittelalter. Von den ersten Kontakten bis zur Fixierung der Kirchenunion im Jahre 1098*, Köln u.a., 1996 (= Forschungen zur Kaiser- und Papstgeschichte des Mittelalters 15).
- 47 This theme is however still exploited by several eleventh and twelfth centuries Greek Byzantine authors in their polemic against the Armenians: T. Kolbaba, „East Roman“, p. 168; A. Bucossi, „Andronico Camatero e la zizzania: sulla politica ecclesiastica bizantina in età comnena“, *Rivista di Studi Bizantini e Neellenici* 47 (2010), pp. 357–371.

At first glance, Piromalli's *Apology* appears to adhere to the patterns of Greek Byzantine anti-Armenian polemics, addressing issues that are predominantly theological and Christological rather than liturgical and ritual. This 'confessionalist' attitude was most likely a reaction and counteroffensive to the rigorous and learned Armenian scholasticism of the monastic schools of Glajor and Tat'ew, on the one hand, and to the miserable and 'ignorant' conditions of the Armenian friars and prelates of the Armenian Catholic Diocese of Naxičewan, on the other hand. Further research into the philosophical and theological underpinnings of the *Apology* would undoubtedly shed light on Piromalli's personality, as well as on this turbulent and late phase of Latin Armenian interconnections within the Persianate cultural sphere of influence.

6 Provisional Conclusions

As I have attempted to demonstrate in this paper, seventeenth-century Armenian eyewitness accounts provide a wealth of material on the highly complex intercommunal and interfaith interactions within and beyond the borders of the Ottoman Empire. The literary texts that allow us to delve into this world are highly diverse, encompassing historical sources, stories of martyrs and converts, accounts of intercommunal or interfaith love affairs, and theological texts. The four case studies discussed here sought to outline the various ways in which different confessional Christian communities within and on the northern and eastern fringes of the Ottoman space interacted, thereby defining the dynamics of conflict and interaction that characterized this period from an Armenian perspective. While this perspective essentially relies on the experiences of educated scholars, it is worth noting that, from the beginning of the seventeenth century onwards, stories about ordinary people became increasingly significant for Ottoman Armenian literati, who incorporated them into their historical narratives, biographical accounts, and diaries. These non-standardized narratives, which make increasing use of the first-person narrator, and anecdotes from the daily lives of the local minority subjects of the Empire, establish a strong intersubjective exchange between narrator and reader. This exchange is intended to foster a sense of communality among distant individuals belonging to the same ethnic and confessional group, while also offering readers a variety of experiences of interaction (whether positive or negative) with others within the confines of the community herself and the supra-communal institutional authority.

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